

Damodar is more salt tolerant than Jaya and regulated Na^+ and K^+ better. For example, at pH 9.8, Damodar had maximum increase of Na^+ (1600%) in the 4th lamina as compared to Jaya's 1178% over the respective controls.

K^+ content of each Damodar lamina decreased less than in Jaya. Reduction in the first lamina over the respective controls was 43% for Damodar and 51% for Jaya. Thus, each part of Damodar had lower Na^+ to K^+ ratio than that of Jaya.

Analysis 60 d after transplanting showed that each leaf sheath had higher Na^+ content than its lamina in both genotypes (see table). The same was true for K^+ for the first and second leaf

Effect of sodicity on Na^+ content of first to fourth laminae (1 L to 4 L) and their sheaths (1 LS to 4 LS) in two rices (% dry weight), Haryana, India.

pH, ESP	Variety	Na^+ content									
		1 L	2 L	3 L	4 L	Mean	1 LS	2 LS	3 LS	4 LS	Mean
8.2	Damodar	0.087	0.070	0.077	0.077	0.078	0.413	0.427	0.473	0.463	0.444
	Jaya	0.093	0.126	0.123	0.143	0.121	0.303	0.410	0.677	0.917	0.577
9.5	Damodar	0.650	0.760	0.903	1.10	0.854	1.21	1.53	1.86	2.12	1.68
	Jaya	0.660	0.737	0.977	1.09	0.867	1.45	1.74	1.92	2.37	1.87
Mean		0.373	0.424	0.520	0.605		0.846	1.029	1.232	1.470	
CD at 5%		$S \times V \times L$ 0.023					$S \times V \times LS$ 0.045				

sheaths at pH 8.1. At pH 9.5, however, each lamina had higher K^+ than its sheath. In both varieties, sodicity decreased K^+ content and increased Na^+ .

Higher Na^+ in older laminae seems to

occur because of its poor retranslocation from older to younger parts. K^+ depletion was highest in older plant parts, suggesting that export of K^+ from older to younger parts exceeded its import under stress. \mathcal{S}

Nitrogen use efficiency in relation to seedling age and transplanting time

P.S. Gill and H. N. Shahi, Punjab Agricultural University (PAU), Rice Research Station (RRS), Kapurthala 144601, India

We studied N use efficiency in terms of grain yield and N recovery in relation to seedling age at transplanting at PAU RRS. The 1981 and 1982 trials were in a split-plot design with 3 transplanting dates (30 Jun, 20 Jul, 9 Aug) and 5 N levels (0, 60, 90, 120, and 150 kg N/ha) as main plots and 3 seedling ages at transplanting (30, 45, and 60 d) as subplots.

PK was applied at 13-25 kg/ha at last puddling. Urea N was applied in equal splits at transplanting, tillering, and panicle initiation. N recovery (kg grain/kg of applied N) was calculated:

$$\text{N recovery} = \frac{\text{Grain yield (kg/ha) in N plots} - \text{Grain yield (kg/ha) in 0 N control}}{\text{N level (kg/ha)}}$$

Transplanting 60-d-old seedlings gave highest grain yield (see figure). The differences in grain yield were most significant at later planting dates. Sixty-day-old seedlings outyielded 30 and 45-d-old seedlings with much higher differences under 0 N as well as under all other N levels with a margin of 0.58-1.1 and 0.184.48 t/ha.

Effect of transplanting schedule, N level, and seedling age on rice grain yield, Kapurthala, India.

Recovery increased with N application. Late-transplanted, 60-d seedlings had much higher N recovery than 30- and 45-d seedlings, although N recovery tended to remain at par for seedlings transplanted 30 Jun and 20 Jul.

The increase in grain yield and N recovery with older seedlings was the net result of balanced dry matter production, early flowering, and high spikelet fertility. \mathcal{S}

Herbicides reduce azolla growth

J.D. Janiya, research assistant, and K. Moody, agronomist, Agronomy Department, IRRI

When azolla is inoculated in transplanted rice fields to fix N, it also competes with weeds by rapidly covering the water surface. However, it does not control all weeds. We studied

the effect of recommended rates of commonly used rice herbicides (see table) on azolla. The study was in a randomized complete block design with four replications.

Azolla caroliniana Willd. was inoculated at 500 g fresh weight/m² immediately after transplanting. Except for oxadiazon applied 3 d before transplanting, all herbicides were applied 4 d after transplanting.

Except for thiobencarb, piperophos - 2, 4-D, and oxadiazon, all herbicides significantly reduced azolla fresh weight by 10 d after treatment. The proprietary mixture of molinate - simetryn - MCPB was most damaging to azolla.

Herbicides did not affect azolla N content.

By 20 d after treatment, all herbicides reduced azolla growth. Molinate - simetryn - MCPB killed all azolla. Thiobencarb was least harmful, reducing

Fresh weight and N content of azolla as affected by herbicide application. ^a IRRI, 1984 wet season.

Treatment	Herbicide rate (kg/ha)	Fresh weight (g/m ²)		N content (%)	
		10 d	20 d	10 d	20 d
Molinate - simetryn - MCPB	0.93	185 f	0 g	2.5 a	—
Butachlor - 2,4-D	1.25	223 ef	32 fg	2.8 a	1.5 a
Butachlor	1.0	310 cdef	77 ef	2.9 a	1.5 a
2,4-D	0.8	216 def	148 ef	2.9 a	2.7 a
Oxyfluorfen	0.14	310 cdef	238 def	2.8 a	2.5 a
Naproanilide - thiobencarb	1.7	348 bcdef	198 defg	2.7 a	2.5 a
Pendimethalin	0.75	383 bcdef	160 efg	2.6 a	2.3 a
Thiobencarb - 2,4-D	1.2	365 bcdef	289 cde	2.6 a	2.4 a
Piperophos - 2,4-D	1.0	485 abcd	191 defg	2.7 a	1.3 a
Oxadiazon	0.75	438 abcde	489 bc	2.5 a	2.6 a
Thiobencarb	1.0	612 a	521 b	2.8 a	2.4 a
Untreated	—	603 a	135 a	2.8 a	2.5 a

^a Observations were made 10 and 20 d after herbicide application. Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

azolla fresh weight 29% compared to the untreated check.

The herbicides had no significant effect on azolla N content. However, had azolla been incorporated 20 d after herbicide application, there would have

been significant differences in the amount of N incorporated because of the different fresh weights.

Weed control measures other than herbicides should be used when azolla is grown. *ℳ*

Effect of soil amendments on summer growth and survival of *Azolla pinnata*

K. Nandabalan and S. Kanaiyan, Agricultural Microbiology Department, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore 641003, Tamil Nadu, India

It is difficult to maintain azolla under field conditions in summer in tropical rice growing areas. We studied the effect of soil amendments on summer azolla growth in Apr 1984.

The experiment was in a randomized block design with 4 replications in 1-m² plots. The following amendments were added to the plots and mixed thoroughly: 50 kg P/ha, 50 kg K, 500 kg neem cake, 50 kg diammonium phosphate, 10 t rice husk, 5 t fresh cow dung, 10 t rice husk, 10 t rice chaff, 5 t farmyard manure, and 10 t sawdust. *Azolla pinnata* was inoculated at 400 g/m² in 10-cm-deep water. Fronds floated on the water for 2 d and then settled on the soil. Soil was kept saturated for 3 wk.

The number of fronds, biomass/10 cm², single frond weight, and root length were recorded. Biomass increased

Effect of soil amendments on azolla growth and survival of azolla in summer, Tamil Nadu, India.

Treatment	Azolla fronds (no./10 cm ²)	Root length (cm)	Single-frond wt (mg)	Biomass (g/10 cm ²)
Control	96	1.4	47.7	14.3
Superphosphate	114	1.2	49.3	15.3
Muriate of potash	107	1.7	49.7	13.0
Neem cake	193	1.8	52.0	20.3
Diammonium phosphate	222	1.9	62.3	23.7
Farmyard manure	88	1.5	45.7	15.3
Cow dung	223	1.3	61.3	22.0
Rice husk	115	2.4	64.3	21.7
Rice chaff	311	1.8	76.3	35.0
Sawdust	99	2.1	44.0	12.7
SE :	4	0.1	2.0	0.6
SEd :	5	0.2	2.8	0.8

over the control in all treatments except that of K and sawdust. The most fronds survived on rice chaff, which gave the highest single frond weight, followed by cow dung and diammonium phosphate. Rice husk gave the longest root length (see table).

Results showed that soil amendments influence azolla growth and survival in summer. Rice chaff increases moisture holding capacity. Allowing azolla to root may enhance survival over maintaining the fronds in floodwater. *ℳ*

Some physiological studies on rice grown on manganese-deficient soil

N. P. Kaur and V. K. Nayyar, Soils Department, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana 141004, India

Wheat grown in rotation with rice on coarse Punjab soils is showing increasing Mn deficiency, but rice has shown no visual symptoms. To understand this tolerance mechanism, we grew PR103 in a Mn-deficient (DTPA Mn 0.8 mg/kg) loamy sand soil